

PURE
3D

The logo for PURE 3D, where 'PURE' is in a dark blue sans-serif font and '3D' is in a larger, bold, dark blue font. The 'D' is stylized with a green and blue geometric mesh pattern.

Guidebook

Making 3D Scholarly Editions Reusable

A step-by-step guide for depositing FAIR 3DSEs

Making 3D Scholarly Editions Reusable

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Maastricht University

Platform Digitale Infrastructuur
Social Sciences & Humanities

¹ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/>

² <https://pure3d.eu/>

³ <https://pdi-ssh.nl/>

⁴ <https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/about-um/faculties/faculty-arts-and-social-sciences>

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1. About this guidebook

This is a guide for making the data of 3D Scholarly Editions (3DSE) reusable. Essential to this is to make the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), and to deposit it in a data repository for safe, long-term storage and retrieval.

Developed in the context of the [PURE3D infrastructure](#),⁵ a **3DSE is a virtual research environment for viewing and editing interactive 3D content for digital heritage and digital humanities**. In the PURE3D infrastructure, creators of 3D content are provided with tools to develop 3DSEs by integrating multiple types of source material, such as annotations, images video, (un)structured data and documents, giving users access to modelling and interpretative choices, creating a multimodal resource that is impossible to replicate in printed form. Preserving and making reusable the data that constitute a 3DSE is the main subject of this guidebook.

The target audience of this document is the research community that creates and uses 3DSEs based on the principles of the PURE3D project. Since the application of open-source and open access principles is a fundamental aspect of the 3DSE, **this guide is also relevant to creators and users of 3D models in general**.

This introductory chapter introduces the **FAIR data principles**, as they are fundamental to data management and sharing. Chapter two of this guidebook describes the **data components of a 3DSE** as implemented by the PURE3D project. The central data object is the 3D model connected to data objects such as annotations, articles, guided tours and narratives. These take the form of digital texts, images, or multimedia files. Using an open-source platform, users can navigate the 3DSE and all included objects. **Archiving 3D models** and their related data objects to enable future access and reuse is the main topic of the third chapter. The FAIR data principles form the basis for decisions on the use of repositories, file formats, and metadata. Chapter four contains a **practical example of a deposit process** of the components of a 3DSE in a repository: [a DANS Data Station](#).⁶

This guidebook is the first approach to an overview of resources and information for making 3D data and related data objects reusable. By addressing both the technical and conceptual challenges of

⁵ PURE3D Infrastructure: <https://editions.pure3d.eu/> and PURE3D Blog: <https://pure3d.eu/>

⁶ <https://dans.knaw.nl/nl/data-stations/>

implementing and preserving 3DSEs, it aims to support the development of sustainable workflows and depositing practices that meet the specific requirements of 3DSEs.

1.1. The importance of making data FAIR

Making data available for reuse allows new research questions to be asked and reduces the cost of collecting data. Making data available has also been shown to enhance the visibility of existing research and allows for research to be reproducible, increasing transparency of the scientific process (Verburg et al., 2023). This principle applies to 3D data, such as 3D data models, as well as related documentation and paradata.

The FAIR data principles provide guidance on how to make data reusable, or “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. The FAIR principles were first published in 2016 (Wilkinson et al., 2016) to provide guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of digital assets, with an emphasis on machine-actionability. These principles support the research data cycle, and as such concern the core values of both the research data repository and its user. The principles refer to three types of entities: data (or any digital object), metadata (information about that digital object), and infrastructure.

To enable researchers to make use of existing data, they should be able to find and access what they need in a data repository. The repository should facilitate this and may have options to enhance the FAIR-ness of a dataset. However, the data creator and the depositor should take actions to provide a dataset in a FAIR manner.

1.1.1. Findable

To begin, it is important to make the data findable by including thorough and accurate metadata. This can include information about the data itself, such as its format and size, as well as contextual information such as the purpose of the data, the methods used to collect it, and any relevant citations. In addition, it is helpful to use standardized terminology and controlled vocabularies to ensure that the data can be easily discovered through keyword searches. See section 3.2.1 on metadata for details on how this is done in the PURE3D project.

It is also critical to make use of **Persistent Identifiers**: permanent, stable references to a resource. When depositing a dataset in a digital repository, a global persistent identifier must be assigned to the dataset, and it must be possible to cite the dataset after publication using the persistent identifier. At DANS, all datasets are assigned a **Digital Object Identifier (DOI)** as a persistent identifier. In PURE3D, the project will include individual persistent identifiers for each edition, including a how-to-cite button to facilitate correct citations.

1.1.2. Accessible

To make the data accessible, it is important that the data is stored in an easily accessible location, by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol. Additionally, clear instructions for accessing and downloading the data are required. **Data should be made accessible, but not all data can always be shared.** Consideration must be given to whether data contains personal information (which privacy protection rules prohibit sharing) or whether there may be other reasons to restrict (in whole or in part) access to data. The creator of the data must specify how the data can be accessed and ensure that the data has an appropriate licence for use.

3DSEs are complex formats that, in addition to 3D models, typically include e.g. videos, photos, and various other media, including from third parties. **In PURE3D, editions can either use any of the [Creative Commons](https://creativecommons.org/)⁷ licences, or use All Rights Reserved.** Editions that include third-party data may not be allowed to distribute this data beyond the edition, and may therefore need to adopt All Rights Reserved copyright. In such cases, the data in question will not be visible in the file lists that are normally found in the Voyager viewer used by PURE3D to display 3DSEs. See the section on Access Conditions (3.2.3) for more details on how to handle such data when depositing your edition.

1.1.3. Interoperable

To ensure that the data is interoperable, it is important to use standard file formats and to document any proprietary file formats or software that may be required to access the data.

When it comes to file formats for 3D data, there are numerous options available, each with their own uses for different academic or professional domains, tools, applications, and operating systems. Although there are at least 140 file formats for 3D data, there is a lack of research on the features and procedures required for 3D file formats (e.g. their relative accessibility, scalability, and device suitability). It may also be difficult to identify which ones are suitable and offer the right features for a certain domain, such as virtual heritage (Champion 2021, 130).

1.1.3. Reusable

The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated or combined in different settings. Prominent aspects of this are that (meta)data must meet domain-relevant community standards and that the (meta)data is released with a clear and accessible usage licence.

The use of 3D models and related data objects in scientific activities poses several challenges that affect its reusability. This includes a lack of standardisation of formats for 3D models, as well as standards for creating metadata and paradata (Papadopoulos 2024, Moore, Rountrey, & Scates Kettler

⁷ <https://creativecommons.org/>

2022). 3D data formats are often very large, negatively affecting both web availability and storage capacity requirements in repositories. Another challenge the lack of browser support for and — related to this — the lack of standardised software to display 3D models over the web.

Therefore, 3D projects often have to rely on proprietary software and customised solutions. **Reliance on commercial and proprietary solutions can make research data vulnerable, should those solutions be changed or discontinued.** A recent example of this is the transition from Sketchfab, a widely used 3D web viewing environment, to Fab, which risks the loss of thousands of 3D models that use the platform. Papadopoulos, Schoueri, & Schreibman (2025) argue that this case demonstrates the need for the 3D cultural heritage sector to transition to an open and sustainable infrastructure that meets the needs of users, which includes many of the solutions for preservation and reuse that will be discussed in this guide.

1.2. Goals of this Guidebook

The purpose of this guidebook is to provide an overview of the steps researchers and data stewards can take when preserving and improving the reliability of data objects that are part of a 3DSE. The guide covers sustainable file formats for 3D models, metadata issues, including usage licences and advice on using repository services for data preservation and access.

The guide thus provides a step-by-guide for how to deposit your 3D data in a FAIR way. This includes particular instructions on how to deposit your data with DANS. However, this is not a requirement, and you can also find guidance on choosing other repositories that suit your data.

This guide is structured around the different steps of depositing 3D data in a data repository:

- **Step 1:** Before depositing (e.g., defining and describing your data, and using the appropriate file formats);
- **Step 2:** During depositing (e.g., entering metadata, defining attributions and access conditions);
- **Step 3:** After depositing (e.g., handling access requests, and keeping data up to date).

2. 3D Scholarly Editions

Before going into the aspects of preservation and reuse of 3D data, we provide the main features of a 3DSE to clarify which specific data objects should be preserved to facilitate future reuse, once the edition is published and ready to be deposited.

2.1. Components of the 3D Scholarly Edition

A **3DSE contains a 3D model of historical or cultural significance**, which not only includes functionalities for inspection of the 3D assets (e.g., zoom in/out, measurement, cross-section, and visual rendering), but also focuses attention on system features that highlight **aspects of digital storytelling** through four distinct but interconnected modalities which provide for exploration both linearly and non-linearly.

3DSE components:

1. **Annotation Labels:** Short, expandable hotspot text as spatially aware annotation;
2. **Articles:** HTML-based pages with text and multimedia that can either overlay the 3D model or be situated to the side of it;
3. **Guided Tours:** A flexible combination of annotation, articles, camera movements and a set of analytic features, such as alternative material shaders, light settings measuring tape and slicer tool;
4. **Audio Narration:** A single audio clip that can be played at any time during the experience.

(Schreibman and Schoueri, 2024)

Figure 2.1: Components of a 3DSE⁸

Figure 2.1 illustrates the **components of a PURE3D 3DSE: 3D model, Annotations, Articles, Guided tour, and Audio Narration (not visible in the figure)**. The 3D model of historical significance takes central place. In this instance, it is a historical building that has been positioned on a historical map for better contextualisation. Annotations are used to highlight specific parts of the model, leading to a short text or a more detailed article.

Articles can be textual, but in most cases, they also include multimedia. The interface of the 3DSE enables advanced navigation functions on the 3D model. The Guided Tour can be activated by using the menu option at the top left of the screen; this provides users with a curated exploration of the 3D scene and its contents. However, users can also explore the 3DSE more freely, by interacting with the 3D model and accessing its various elements in a nonlinear fashion.

⁸ Source: 3DSE "Diaconie Weeshuis"
<https://editions.pure3d.eu/project/7/edition/1/>

The 3DSE is viewed using the open-source **Smithsonian Voyager** web explorer that has been created specifically for displaying, exploring, and sharing rich 3D data and models of museum collections and cultural heritage.⁹ 3DSEs can be conceived in terms of three interoperable tiers or layers:

Three layers of 3DSEs:

1. **The viewer layer** (what the user sees);
2. **The database layer** that contains the version of the 3D model used in the interface, as well as information contained in the annotation and information about the behaviour of these objects;
3. **The preservation layer** which can house all the versions of the model created, as well as the metadata and paradata.

(Schreibman and Schoueri, 2024, p.23)

Figure 2.2 illustrates the architecture of the 3DSE as developed in the PURE3D project. The 3D model and related objects, such as annotations, are stored in a database that is accessed by a web application that makes the 3D model and related information visible to a user interactively. The database and web application are the main objects for which preservation and reuse activities are described in the next section of this guidebook.

Figure 2.2: Infrastructure of the PURE3D 3D Scholarly Edition¹⁰

⁹ <https://smithsonian.github.io/dpo-voyager/>

¹⁰ PURE3D GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/CLARIAH/pure3dx/blob/main/docs/architecture.md>

2.2. Features of 3D Scholarly Editions

The PURE3D project has defined requirements for 3D scholarly editions to be included in the 3DSE platform. These requirements can be used to get an understanding of the types of data objects that should be preserved and for which preservation guidelines are defined in this guidebook.

PURE3D formulated submission guidelines for participation in the process to create the publication of a peer-reviewed 3D Scholarly Edition. The guidelines cover details on the 3D model as well as on metadata and paradata and require some expert knowledge on how to create 3D data models.¹¹ Below, the submission guidelines are provided with some additional explanatory information:

3D models can be in the form of digitised objects, structures, landscapes etc. or reconstructed environments in computer graphics. Models can be project-specific or created by a heritage institution, be free from copyright (or copyright is explicitly obtained), and meet the requirements listed below:

PURE3D technical requirements for 3DSEs:

- **.gltf/.glb data format**¹² for the 3D model (open-source Draco Compression is advised for .glb files).
- **Including PBR (Physical-Based Rendering)** extensions that conform to the three.js standard (a cross-browser JavaScript library and API (application programming interface) used to create and display animated 3D computer graphics in a web browser.¹³
- For single digitised objects, one 4K (= raster of 4096 × 4096 pixels) **texture map** (in .jpg file format¹⁴ with 86 compression). For complex scenes, the textures of the various parts should conform to the 1024 × 1024 texture standard.
- **Model size maximum:** 230,000 triangles for all geometry in the scene. This ensures good performance but can be higher if it is a complex object/scene. (A triangle is the fundamental geometrical shape). This maximum setting prevents the file size of the 3D model from becoming too large, and thus 3D scenes can also be viewed on mobile devices.
- **Essential model information:** geometry, texture, and normals (vectors perpendicular to a surface that defines the orientation of that surface and thus are critical for lighting, shading, and rendering processes)). Please note that other 3D model elements, e.g., lights, cameras, colour vertex information are not needed since they are not supported by Voyager Explorer.

¹¹ These guidelines are published at: <https://pure3d.eu/submission-guidelines/>

¹² The glTF data format is a “preferred data format” for 3D data, see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/3d/gltf/>

¹³ Note: PBR defines a standard set of parameters that are used to simulate real-world lighting interactions, materials, and surface properties

¹⁴ The JPEG image format is a “preferred data format”, see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/images-raster/jpeg/>

Metadata that can be included in the edition:

- Where and when the edition is focused, the subject (e.g. archaeology);
- the technology used to create the 3D model (e.g. 3D reconstruction, photogrammetry etc.);
- rights holder and rights licence (i.e. CC-BY).

Metadata will be collected separately by the PURE3D team before publication. When depositing a 3DSE, authors may want to provide additional metadata to 3D models and related digital objects. See section 3.2.1. for additional details on this.

Paradata¹⁵ that can be included in the edition:

- An explanation on how the data was created (techniques or recording systems);
- Choices made in the digitization process, including manipulations made to the 3D model;
- Which sources were used for reconstructions and why, and any uncertainties encountered during the 3D creation;
- Explanation for the secondary use of 3D models: even in cases where the 3D model is not an original creation (e.g., it may be downloaded from a 3D repository) paradata can still be included along with a note on why this particular model was chosen to represent the narrative.

2.3. File formats used in a 3D Scholarly Edition

An important aspect of preserving a 3DSE is the file formats of the data components that comprise the 3DSE. Ideally, open (i.e., non-proprietary) standardised file formats should be used, as they allow optimal reuse and long-term usability.

The most essential part of a 3DSE is the 3D model, for which the **standard file format .gltf/.glb** is used. Moreover, the annotations, articles, and multimedia use standard file formats such as **.html, .jpg, .png and .mp4**.

The Smithsonian Voyager system uses a custom document format, **.svx (Smithsonian Voyager eXperience)**, an openly available and well-documented file format used to describe 3D scenes.¹⁶ Although the .svx format is similar to the widely used .gltf format described above, they are not directly compatible with each other. However, the structure is similar enough for people familiar with the .gltf

¹⁵ Paradata is information about human processes of understanding and interpretation of data objects. Examples of paradata include descriptions stored within a structured dataset of how evidence was used to interpret an artefact, or a comment on methodological premises within a research publication (London Charter, 2009b. Cited in Papadopoulos, 2024).

¹⁶ The .svx file format is documented at:

<https://smithsonian.github.io/dpo-voyager/document/overview/>

format to understand it. As .svx is a custom and non-standard file format, researchers should ensure that any use of it is described in detail and refers to the associated documentation so that any user unfamiliar with it can understand and reuse it.

Another file format used by the 3DSE platform is the **.yaml file format**¹⁷ aimed at data interchange, often used for writing configuration files. It is also human-readable. It is an open format and contains the metadata fields and metadata content of a 3DSE project and its related 3DSE editions. Examples of metadata fields in the .yaml files are “title”, “creator” and “abstract”.

In conclusion, the file formats used by 3DSEs facilitate preservation and future reuse because they apply commonly used and open standards. However, preservation and reuse of data objects has many more aspects such as documenting data files, provision of licences, secure storage in trusted digital repositories and the application of persistent identifiers. This is covered in the next section.

¹⁷ The YAML specification is published at: <https://yaml.org/>

3. Preserving and Publishing 3D Scholarly Edition Data

Long-term preservation of all versions of 3D models, as well as metadata and paradata, requires services and procedures that are further elaborated in this section. It is important to distinguish between providing 3D models for online use on the one hand, and archiving the 3D data objects on the other.

The following sections outline the practical steps of preserving and publishing 3D data for reuse, divided into the stages of before, during, and after the depositing of data. Finally, this section describes an example data deposit of a 3DSE in which the practical steps described are applied.

3.1. Before Depositing

3.1.1. Defining a Dataset

It is worthwhile thinking about how your dataset can be defined. This is important to ensure that others can understand and replicate a research project, as well as impacting what data is stored and in which repository (e.g., a domain-specific one; see section 3.1.3), as well as what metadata is used (section 3.2.1).

Before submitting data to a repository, it is important to have an overview of the collection of data files that will be archived. The “download” function, available on the project page of the 3DSE Author Web Interface,¹⁸ will create a folder and subfolders on the file system on the local computer with all files that are needed to compile the 3DSE. It is this collection of data files, or a subset thereof, that should be stored in a digital repository to facilitate long-term access and reuse.¹⁹ Again, additional files not strictly

¹⁸ <https://author.pure3d.eu/> - editable only by authenticated users

¹⁹ Chapter 4 illustrates the depositing process of the components of a 3DSE in a data repository.

Research data can be defined in terms of:

1. **Origins and mode of collection:** e.g., derived data, observations, or models/simulations
2. **Data types:** e.g., digital objects, spreadsheets, audio, meta/paradata, and/or text documents
3. **Formats:** e.g., textual (.txt, .pdf, ...), software code (Java, Python, ...), or software/instrument specific (Blender 3D data, Carl Zeiss Digital Microscopic Image Format (ZVI))
4. **Size & complexity:** e.g., individual large files, sets of smaller files, or combinations thereof
5. **Research phase:** e.g., raw, processed, analysed, or (pre-)published data

(CESSDA Training Team, 2020, p. 13; Scott & Cox, 2016)

part of the 3DSE can also be archived: e.g., images used to generate 3D models, supporting documents, and README documents for users of deposited data.²⁰

We have noted that 3DSEs contain multiple data types and data formats. In addition, they have particular **structural characteristics** that may be useful for users of the data (Papadopoulos & Schreibman, 2019; Schreibman & Gillikin Schoueri, 2024):

Structure of a 3DSE

- **Edition:** describing e.g., the context, aims, composition, and intended use thereof, as well as its relation to the broader research project and other editions (if applicable);
- **3D viewer:** briefly describe the use of the Voyager 3D viewer, refer to documentation from Smithsonian,²¹ as well as how .json and .html files in the dataset are used to configure the viewer and the content;
- **Annotations:** explicit (e.g., linked data from external sources, audio, video, short textual explanations), and implicit (camera movements, layers, object configurations).

Much of this information may already be contained in (un)published reports of the research. **It may be useful to include or refer to this information, along with any additional information not recorded elsewhere, in the data documentation (section 3.1.2.1) that is deposited together with the data.**

3.1.2. Describing a dataset

Before submitting your data, it is important to thoroughly describe and organise your data so that it can be properly understood and reused. **Doing so reduces the risk for misinterpretation, facilitates FAIR data sharing and reuse, and thereby maximises the impact of your data.**²²

²⁰ For more details on what data to preserve, see section 3.1.3

²¹ <https://smithsonian.github.io/dpo-voyager/>

²² For a good example of clear and descriptive documentation, see: van Wissen, Leon; Vriend, Nico; Nijssen, Antoinet; Vereecken, Lars; den Engelse, Menno, 2024, "FAIR Photos - CLARIAH FAIR Data Call 2023", <https://doi.org/10.17026/SS/7VD3ME>, DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities, V1

3.1.2.1. Documentation

Good documentation of a dataset includes:

- **A data overview:** including its purposes, methodology, scope, and features (see the “Defining a Dataset” section above for additional details).
- **The dataset structure:** including e.g. where the image files used for which 3D models can be found
- **File list:** For datasets with many files, it may also be advisable to provide a file list, listing file names or folders (if a dataset contains e.g. hundreds of images, you can refer to groups of files rather than individual ones), descriptions of their contents, and of any connections between the files. If your dataset contains HTML files, it may also be helpful to provide an index file, making it possible to browse through different HTMLs as they would be displayed;
- **A codebook:** where applicable, including a codebook listing e.g. variable descriptions, definitions, and descriptions of data transformations
- **Software and version details:** including scripts used to process the data
- **Instructions for reuse:** provide any additional information necessary to reuse the data, e.g. which files, software, and codes are necessary for different purposes.

3.1.2.2. Organising data

Before submitting your data, you may also need to ensure that your dataset structure is understandable, and that any unsuitable files have been removed:

- **Reduce folder hierarchy:** where possible, avoid folder structures where files are nested under multiple levels of folders, making them difficult to navigate
- **Remove personal information:** Ensure that file names do not contain any personal information, as these may become publicly visible
- **Remove unused files:** any unused or duplicate files should be removed, as they will increase the size and complexity of the dataset

3.1.2.3. Preserving the 3D viewer layer

As described in section 2.1., a 3DSE can be thought of as consisting of three interlinked layers: the Viewer, Database, and Preservation layers. Depositing data with DANS or other repositories will typically preserve the latter two layers, containing data and/or metadata, by default. However, **the Viewer layer, which is how users experience the dataset in the Voyager 3D viewer, is not preserved by default.** Therefore, should Voyager at some point in the future become unavailable, users of the data may not be able to reliably recreate how the data was presented in the 3D viewer. **A simple method to preserve the viewer layer is to capture images or videos, e.g. in the form of**

screencasts of the 3DSE as it would be experienced by users.²³ Screencasts can be created, e.g. using native macOS or Windows screencast software. Once created, these can be deposited along with the other data in the dataset.

3.1.3. Selecting Data to Deposit

Research projects typically produce a lot of data and supplementary materials, not all of which needs to be deposited for the long term. Research Data Netherlands (RDNL) lists the following general [reasons to preserve research data](#):²⁴

- **The importance of the data:** potential value for reuse, (inter)national positioning and quality, originality, size, scale, the production costs of the data or, for example, the innovative nature of the research.
- **The uniqueness of the data:** the data includes non-repeatable observations.
- **The importance of the data for historical research,** in particular scientific-historical research.
- **The research data are important for non-scientific purposes** (cultural heritage, museums, or presentations)

The types and amounts of data to be archived will be determined by its intended purpose and audience. One aspect regards **quality**. For example, many researchers, including archaeologists and engineers, typically require high quality 3D models. On the other hand, 3D models used in creative industries or education tend to suffice with lower quality (European Commission 2022, 4). Such considerations may also apply to images or video. Typically, higher quality means that more storage space is needed. Therefore, unless the project in question requires high data quality, **consider selecting lower or medium quality versions of files where possible**, thereby reducing data complexity and storage costs, and making the data more reusable and sustainable. **If higher quality data is needed for the project or for other users of the data, then consider preserving this instead of the lower quality data.**

Another aspect concerns **which data to store**. For example, many datasets contain **supplementary materials**, data not used or presented in the project outputs, or photos used to generate 3D models. In some cases, such data may not need to be preserved, while in others, it may merit preservation. Consider the general reasons to preserve data listed above, as well as project-specific needs. The choice of what data to store is ultimately up to the user.

²³ An example of a deposited 3D visualisation can be found at: D Nagel; T. Cocquyt, 2013, "Animated, interactive 3D visualization of a corn mill, after a description by Ramelli", <https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-zzq-ymge>, DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities, V1

²⁴ <https://researchdata.nl/en/services/datamanagement/>

3.1.4. Select a Repository

The characteristics of a repository are important to making data FAIR. For example, a repository can attach globally unique persistent identifiers to data files or have facilities to manage access to data files based on access licences attributed to the dataset by its owner.

The PURE3D project produced a report that investigates the landscape of repositories and their suitability for 3DSEs in detail (Fung et al. 2021), and Dataverse, (the repository system used by DANS as basis for its Data Stations) is identified as one of three recommended repository systems.

The Registry of Research Data Repositories (Re3Data²⁵) provides a comprehensive listing of data repositories that can be used to facilitate the archiving of datasets. Because 3D data models are not standardized and often use significant data volumes, there are a limited number of solutions available that allow long-term access and reuse of these types of data objects.

Considerations when selecting a long-term repository for 3DSEs:

- **Is the repository certified?**

A data repository can be regarded as a *Trusted Digital Repository (TDR)* if it is certified according to international standards. The CoreTrustSeal²⁶ is regarded as core level certification for data repositories. DANS ensures that the datasets are archived in a certified TDR.

- **Does the repository charge costs?**

DANS presently offers its services free of charge for individual researchers with datasets up to 50 GB per account. The rate for depositing larger files needs to be discussed with DANS and is determined by several factors (see the DANS website for additional details²⁷)

- **Does the repository accommodate the data?**

You may have specific requests for the metadata fields which are available to you; for the access settings; for the ways the data can be displayed; and, for the target audience of the repository. For the DANS Data Stations, this guide will inform you regarding the metadata and accessibility options.

If you decide to deposit your dataset in a DANS Data Station, you will still need to select **which Data Station to use**. DANS has four domain-specific Data Stations:²⁸ a **Data Station for Archaeology, Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)**, **Physical & Technical Sciences**, and a **Data Station for Life**

²⁵ <https://www.re3data.org/>

²⁶ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

²⁷ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/rate-information/>

²⁸ See the following link for details on these: <https://dans.knaw.nl/nl/data-stations/>

Sciences. All four Data Stations are directed towards their respective research communities, and feature discipline-specific vocabularies. Although they make use of the same general metadata schemas, they use different **specific metadata blocks that enable standardised input from domain-specific dictionaries**, easily entered using autocomplete functionality.²⁹

For 3D data of historical models, a choice needs to be made between the Data Station Archaeology and the Data Station SSH. In case the dataset is of great interest to the archaeological community, DANS would recommend using the Data Station Archaeology. Please take into account that the Data Station Archaeology is also used for the archiving of datasets pertaining to Building History/History of arts and architecture.

3.1.5. Preferred File Formats

Using open and interoperable file formats is crucial to making your data reusable. Despite the large number of file formats for 3D models, regarding long-term usability, it is difficult to identify certain formats that are preferred or recommended over others. Generally, different 3D software use their own formats, interoperability is limited, and the conversion of formats can lead to the loss of functionality or of certain properties.

Therefore, **3D models are best preserved in their original file format whenever possible**, but there may be reasons and situations where converting to another file format is advisable, such as when storing data for optimal interoperability and long-term access. DANS maintains a list of preferred file formats that they are convinced are suitable for long-term preservation, based on international agreements.

Formats suitable for long-term preservation are generally:

- frequently used;
- have open specifications; and
- are independent of specific software, developers, or vendors.

Given the pros and cons of file conversion just described, it is often the best solution to deposit your data in both a file format that is suitable or available for the task at hand, and in a format that is better suited for long-term preservation.

²⁹ For example, the Data Station Archaeology includes such a metadata block with a selection of terminology fields from the national Dutch archaeological vocabulary, the 'Archeologisch Basis Register' (Archaeological Basic Registry, ABRplus). The Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities includes a vocabulary for key terms from the European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST), a topic classification for the Consortium of European Social Sciences Data Archives (CESSDA) as well as more free text metadata fields to provide descriptions on data collection and composition common in the Social Sciences.

3.1.5.1. 3D File Formats

Regarding the file format of the 3D models in the 3DSE, PURE3D requirements indicate that the .gltf/.glb data format should be used (as detailed in section 2.2.). DANS regards **.gltf/.glb 2.0** as a “preferred format”. It is a frequently used format, with [open specifications](#)³⁰, that is developed by the open and non-profit Khronos Group consortium ([Khronos Group, 2020; Flohr et al., 2024, p. 13](#)). It is important to note that version 2.0 of .gltf/.glb that was released in 2017 is significantly more preservable than the earlier, 1.0 version, which is considered by DANS a non-preferred format.

Therefore, make sure that any .glTF files you deposit are version 2.0.

The remaining 3DSE requirements listed above (e.g., regarding model size and information) have no impact on the ability to deposit at DANS, however users should make sure that format specifications enable reusability by conforming to good practice and standards wherever possible.

The .gltf/.glb file format is not the only file format suitable for long-term access. Other 3D file formats can also be classified as “preferred formats”. There are many file formats for 3D models, and it is difficult to pinpoint certain formats that are preferred over others. In some cases, 3D software uses its own proprietary file format that limits interoperability.

The PURE3D project made an analysis of different 3D file formats in a [Technical Report](#),³¹ containing information on which formats different institutions recommend for the preservation of 3D content ([Fung et al., 2021, pp. 11–12](#)). For 3D models, it is particularly important to consider whether the format in question supports all properties that the model contains.

3.1.5.2. Other file formats

3DSEs usually contain other types of data beyond 3D models, such as text, audio, and markup language, which also need to be evaluated based on their reusability and interoperability. It may also be worth considering if certain formats are more suitable in your particular project, discipline, or application — e.g., in terms of interoperability, usability, or common practice. For example, some file formats may require proprietary software to open, thereby limiting reusability. DANS, however, makes exceptions for proprietary formats that are frequently used in certain fields (e.g. Esri Shapefiles, Microsoft Access databases, or SPSS .sav files). With such formats, DANS asks users to preserve the data in *both* the original non-preferred format, as well as converted to a preferred format.

An overview of (non-) preferred file formats of commonly used data types is made available by [DANS](#).³² If depositing data with DANS, **consider reviewing this table to see if the file formats used in your data are appropriate.** If you are using a different repository, or your format cannot be found in the

³⁰ <https://www.khronos.org/Gltf>

³¹ https://pure3d.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Pure3D_Technical-Report.pdf

³² See: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

aforementioned list, alternative sources of information include: the Archeology Data Service (ADS) [file formats overview](#)³³ (Archeology Data Service, n.d.), [a recent 4CH report](#)³⁴ on the reusability of 3D data (Flohr et al., 2024, p. 13), or an exhaustive [EU report on 3D data in cultural heritage](#) (European Commission, 2022, p. 74).

3.2. During Deposit

The following instructions apply to depositing data with DANS. Note that other repositories may use other specific procedures, but that the general principles described here are generally applicable.

3.2.1. Metadata

Metadata is data associated with an information object for purposes of description, administration, legal requirements, technical functionality, use and usage, and preservation. To make data FAIR, it is essential to select a suitable metadata schema for citing and describing data. It is common for metadata schemas to include mandatory metadata fields as well as optional metadata fields. For example, **fields for entering a dataset title; the primary author(s); and, a brief description, are normally mandatory fields.** Many optional fields may not always be relevant, but it is recommended to make use of as many metadata fields as possible for high findability and reusability of the dataset.

The metadata templates, as used by DANS in the DANS Data Stations (based on Dataverse), lend itself very well to providing 3DSE datasets with rich metadata. Dataverse uses standard-compliant metadata from international standards including DDI, DataCite and DCMI to ensure that the metadata is easy to map and to export for preservation and interoperability purposes.³⁵

3.2.1.1. DANS-required metadata

Dataverse metadata is divided into several blocks, starting with '**Citation Metadata**': this block provides the mandatory fields: **Title; Author; Point of Contact; Description; Subject** (area of study relevant to the dataset, selected from a controlled vocabulary). It is important to give a concise summary for the **Description**, which makes it clear to any user what the dataset is about. The **Description** is displayed directly on the landing page, and the first 280 characters are displayed in search and browse results. The **Description** field is repeatable: it could be an option to first enter an abstract, then repeat the field for entering a lengthier description.

³³ archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/help-guidance/guides-to-good-practice/data-analysis-and-visualisation/3d-models/creating-3d-data/file-formats/

³⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/10200379>

³⁵ Further information on metadata and other aspects to consider while depositing data at DANS can be found at:

https://dans.knaw.nl/en/depositing-data-manual/during-depositing_ds/

In the block '**Rights Metadata**', the individual or organisational **Rights Holder** needs to be specified. Users must also specify whether the data contains **personal data** as defined by GDPR regulations. In short, this implies any information which is related to an identified or identifiable natural person.³⁶

Finally, the '**Relation Metadata**' block includes a mandatory field to specify the Audience for which the dataset is relevant: one or more options from a standardised vocabulary of scientific disciplines need to be selected. Optionally, relations to other sources are registered here. Relations can be other datasets or publications, but also references to hosting pages, holding institutions or web sources such as a viewer or a scholarly edition page. It is also possible to assign a dataset to a **Collection**, chosen from a controlled vocabulary. These collections can be collections of organisations, of institutions, or of larger projects. DANS can add new names to the collection vocabulary if the collection is of substantial size and is a logical entry point for facilitating reuse of the data. 3DSEs within the PURE3D project, which use a hierarchical structure of Projects with multiple associated Editions, is a good use case for the use of relation metadata.

3.2.1.2. Additional metadata

Additionally, the Citation Metadata block has optional fields to describe: **a Subtitle; Alternative Titles/URLs; Identifiers; Contributors; Keywords; a Production Date; Producer, Production Place, Publisher information; Series information; the Data Source, the Kind of Data, and more.** An **Alternative Title** is a title by which a work is commonly referred to or an abbreviation of the title, but could also be used to give a one-line abstract description, or even to clarify that a dataset is part of a larger project. The **Series** metadata is very useful when the dataset is one self-contained part of a larger project. The **Keyword** field is very flexible and can be filled in with free text; it is also possible to refer to existing vocabularies. There is a general metadata field for **Notes**, which can be used for any extra information or clarification that cannot be specified in other fields.

The **Contributor** metadata field, used for names of individuals and/or organisations which contributed to the dataset, includes a vocabulary with terms from the international standard DataCite to specify the type/role of the contributor. **For 3DSE datasets, it may be desirable to specify that certain people were responsible for certain parts of the data**, such as the creator of a 3D model that is part of the dataset. However, such details are too specific to describe using the DataCite vocabulary. In this case and in similar instances where extra details are wanted but cannot fit in the metadata schemes, it is always an option to use the Description or the Notes field to enter the additional information.

The metadata block '**Temporal and Spatial Coverage**' can be used to specify locations and time periods or time spans covered by the data, including spatial locations using coordinates (central points or a spatial box with the outermost coordinates).

³⁶ <https://gdpr-info.eu/issues/personal-data/>

3.2.2. Privacy and data protection

Consider what privacy and data protection considerations apply to your data, and if or to what extent the data can be made public. Personal data, as defined by the EU's [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#)³⁷, is any information that can identify a living person, either directly or indirectly. This includes names, identification numbers, location data, online identifiers, or characteristics related to a person's physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity. Personal data can be protected through **anonymization or pseudonymization**. Anonymized data is not considered personal data, but pseudonymized data is still regarded as personal data.

If your data contains the types of personal information listed above, and you believe that privacy and data protection considerations may apply, further information, as well as tools for protecting personal data (thereby making it publishable) can be found on the [DANS website](#).³⁸

3.2.3. Access conditions

A data repository should allow the depositor to manage the accessibility of their datasets. There are means to specify which parts of the dataset can be accessed, and there are also options regarding the conditions under which the accessed data can be reused. **The depositor should consider legal requirements and demands or protocols from their organisation or discipline.**

There should always be a consideration if personal data was collected in the meaning of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). **The depositor also needs to make sure that the data they deposit is indeed theirs to deposit and their dataset does not include data from third parties with existing copyrights and licences.** If so, the data should be **removed** from the dataset and references to the third-party sources need to be entered in the dataset metadata. Third-party data may be included if the depositor can ensure that re-sharing the data is allowed in accordance with the pre-existing licences.

When a user accesses a file from the dataset, the user is bound to the conditions stated in the dataset licence for reuse of the data. The depositor can select a dataset licence from a number of Creative Commons Open Access licences, or alternatively a specific licence for restricted data. It is not possible to have more than one licence for a single dataset. For best research practices, it is encouraged that data is as much as possible published publicly accessible with an **Open Access licence**, and clear restricted access options are stated for sensitive (meta)data. DANS maintains a handy [list of open](#)

³⁷ <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/>

³⁸ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/news/how-to-deposit-personal-data/>

[licences](#)³⁹ as well as their conditions. In addition, DANS maintains a [comprehensive guide for depositing data under restrictive licence conditions](#)⁴⁰.

Depending on the data repository, there may be more options to **manage data access**. The Dataverse-based DANS Data Stations allow the depositor to specify per data file whether access is restricted or not. Should one or more files be set to restricted access, it normally means that other users first need to submit an access request to the depositor. These access requests are submitted via the system and mailed to the depositor, who is asked to grant or deny the request.

Additionally, an **embargo** can be set per data file, which disables accessibility options for users until the embargo expires. Depositors can also **restrict access** to individual files, if the use of these files is allowed under certain conditions. This requires users to request access to the file before they can access it.

3.2.3 Submission

Once the above steps are completed, the data needs to be uploaded and typically submitted for review by the repository before being published. Note that repositories often have restrictions regarding the size and format of the data uploaded. At DANS, data below 50 GB can be uploaded for free (for higher amounts, costs may be involved). When uploading data files, a collection of files can be submitted in a single ZIP file, which will automatically be extracted during the upload.

Submitted data will typically be assigned a **DOI (Digital Object Identifier)**, which is a persistent identifier that can be used to reference a dataset. When you deposit a dataset at DANS, a DOI will be automatically assigned to the dataset. The DOI is reserved when depositing and will become active after publication of the dataset.

3.3. After Depositing

3.3.1. Changing your Dataset after Publication

After a dataset has been published, there may be several reasons to revise it: (meta)data may need to be added or updated; access conditions changed; or errors may need to be addressed. Many research projects, including those of PURE3D, are regularly updated to include updated or new data.

At DANS and several other repositories, revising a dataset will create a new version of your dataset deposit, rather than a new deposit. At DANS, revisions to an existing dataset will be reviewed by a DANS

³⁹ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/licences/>

⁴⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10887484>

data manager before a new version with the same DOI as the previous version or versions is created. Previous versions will remain accessible, unless one or more versions are requested to be *deaccessioned*.

Whether a **new version** should be created may depend on the versioning policies of the repository; the needs of the target audience; or the nature of the change. For example, error fixes or new data may need to be added immediately, while minor changes may be added in intermediate updates. Any time a new version is added, it is advisable to document which changes were made and to outline any update/maintenance plans should these exist. In the DANS Data Stations, any changes to an existing dataset will automatically be listed in the Versions tab of the dataset.

3.3.2. Access Requests & Inquiries

After a dataset has been published, users may contact the assigned contact person of the data for inquiries. For restricted data, access requests may be submitted for the data in question. **Depositors should always remember to use contact details that will remain stable over the long term.**

3.3.3. Citing your dataset

For 3D models, attributing authorship may be complicated: the author may be considered the modeller(s), the edition editor, or if the 3D model is a reproduction of a physical object, the creator of that object. Schreibman & Gillikin Schoueri (2024, p. 18) argue that there is a strong case to consider the 3D modeller as the author, but other considerations may apply.

When citing your dataset, it is advisable to adhere to certain best practices to make citing easier and more user-friendly. DANS adheres to the [Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles](#),⁴¹ and requests that citations include: name(s) and/or organisation of the dataset creator(s); publishing year; dataset title; persistent identifier (DOI) of the dataset as a URL; the repository name; and (if applicable) version number.

⁴¹ <https://force11.org/info/joint-declaration-of-data-citation-principles-final/>

4. Use Case: Depositing 3DSE Data

This section demonstrates the steps for depositing a 3DSE in a repository, using the Diaconie Weeshuis 3DSE and the DANS Archaeology Data Station as example

The deposit of 3DSE data refers to the process of transferring relevant data files that are part of a 3DSE to a digital archive to facilitate future access and reuse. In addition to the 3D model and related digital objects (annotations, articles, multimedia), additional data files can also be transferred, such as 3D data models related to the subject of the 3DSE but not included in the online edition, or files that can be considered as paradata.

4.4.1. Metadata fields of 3DSE Projects and Editions

The goal of FAIR data submission is to document and format the data objects in such a way that a future “**designated community**” can find, understand and reuse the data, under appropriate access conditions. A key aspect of the data submission process is the creation of metadata of the data objects so they can be properly understood and reused, ideally both by machines and people.

The **granularity of the metadata**, i.e., which components of a 3DSE are described and archived, and the quality of the metadata, i.e., level of detail and accuracy, largely determine the extent to which the data are FAIR (section 1.1.). The metadata fields should contain all relevant details of the data files that comprise a 3DSE, and the storage system should enable the storage and retrieval of the metadata and related data objects, including their underlying relationships.

One or more Editions are part of a 3DSE Project. The “[Vlooienburg Jewish Amsterdam](#)” 3DSE project⁴² currently has two published editions, including the “Diaconie Weeshuis” edition which is the basis for this use case.⁴³ Another example is the “[Let There Be Light](#)” project, containing multiple editions describing mining lamps.⁴⁴ An advantage of this approach is that when a 3DSE is expanded in the future, new 3D models can be added to the Project, e.g., when a new model of a mining lamp becomes available.

⁴² <https://editions.pure3d.eu/project/3/>

⁴³ See: T. Lanjouw, 2025, "3D scholarly edition for the "Diaconie Weeshuis", Amsterdam (1656-1888).", <https://doi.org/10.17026/AR/Z2FNTQ>, DANS Data Station Archaeology, V1

⁴⁴ <https://editions.pure3d.eu/project/2/>

The 3DSE includes the following **project-level metadata fields**, contained in the file “**project.yaml**”:

- Title
- Abstract
- Contributor
- Coverage
 - Period
 - Place
- Creator
- Institution
- Language
- Subject (1 or more subject headings)
- Date published

The 3DSE provides the following **edition-level fields**, provided in the file “**edition.yaml**”:

- Title
- Subtitle
- Abstract
- Creators
- Date published
- Rights
- Licence
- Rights holder
- Contact
- Keywords
- Audience
- Funder
- Countries
- Latitude/Longitude
- Place
- Period
- Temporal
- Subjects
- Languages
- Sources
- Provenance
- Voyager version

These project- and edition-level metadata fields should be compatible with the data repository. Additionally, the data repository will add a number of additional **repository-specific metadata elements**:

- Persistent identifier (created and managed by the repository)
- Licence / data use agreement (the type of usage licence connected to the project, e.g. open, closed or restricted access).

4.4.2. Defining the structure of the deposit

There are three alternatives to structure the components of a 3DSE (Project, Editions, Models etc.) into single entities of datasets suitable for archiving, reusing and referencing. It is up to the depositor to decide which alternative to choose.

1. **All the data for all Editions go into one dataset, with project- and selected edition-level metadata.** The metadata is mainly based on the content of the “project.yaml” file, with optional additions from the “edition.yaml” files where relevant and desired, e.g. for keywords and other details to make these explicitly searchable and findable. The data is structured in folders, with each Edition in a separate folder.
2. **Create an individual dataset for each individual Edition.** Mainly use the “edition.yaml” file for the metadata (for example, the abstract can be used as the dataset description); include general Project metadata with all individual Edition datasets belonging to the same project (use the ‘Series’ field for a general project description taken from the “project.yaml” file); additionally datasets can be related to each other via the ‘Relations’ field. Should there be dozens of datasets belonging to the same Project, a standardized collection name can be made available for the metadata field ‘Collection’.
3. **Same as option 2 but also create a general Project dataset**, which can be the central focus of relations to the individual Edition datasets. This option can only be used if there are general data files covering the entire Project to upload with such a general dataset, as it is undesirable to publish an ‘empty’ dataset (without any data). This option can also be used to archive the paradata (see definition on page 13) of the project.

The [‘Diaconie Weeshuis’](#) edition from the Vlooienburg Project (described on page 27) was deposited at DANS following option 2. The following section demonstrates how this can be done. This edition generally provides a good example for how 3DSEs can be deposited. **We recommend readers of this guide to explore this deposit** to see how the data from a 3DSE can be structured.

4.4.3. Depositing process

Depositing the files of a 3DSE in a DANS data station consists of nine steps. These steps can be divided into three categories:

1. Downloading the data files of the 3DSE (step 1-3)
2. Creating a record⁴⁵ in the DANS data station with appropriate metadata fields (step 4-6)
3. Populating the record with content (step 7-9)

Below, each of the steps is described in more detail using the '[Diaconie Weeshuis](#)' edition described in the previous section, using option #2: "Creating an individual dataset for each individual Edition."

1. **Download** all files of the 3DSE to a local hard drive by using the "download" function in the PURE3D "[author](#)" interface (see Figure 4.1), either for an individual edition, or the entire project including all editions.⁴⁶ Downloading a project will result in a file structure as seen in Figure 4.2:

Figure 4.1: Download function in 3DSE authoring system

Name	^	Date Modified	Size	Kind
▼ edition	☁	14:36	--	Folder
> 64eca657b1520537c7ac5b08	☁	14:36	--	Folder
> 67c5628b028ff3ef338e60e3	☁	14:36	--	Folder
🖼 icon.png	☁	03/04/2025	2,1 MB	PNG image
📄 project.yaml	☁	12:35	2 KB	text document

Figure 4.2: 3DSE project file structure

2. **Rename** the folder names. The initial names of the folders are strings of characters and numbers without any semantics. In this example, the project has two editions which have not yet been renamed, which can be found in the subfolders under the "edition" folder. The editions may themselves have subfolder which may need to be renamed, e.g. for articles, or photos.
3. **Organise** the files that need to be deposited, e.g., high resolution 3D model, paradata, etc., a subfolder with a suitable name should be created, e.g., named "additional material", "high resolution model", "paradata", etc. The folders should then be populated with the appropriate files that should be included in the archived 3DSE.

⁴⁵ In the Dataverse system a record is called "Dataverse". A Dataverse consists of 1 or more files. In this use-case the Dataverse created gets the same name as the name of the 3DSE Project.

⁴⁶ Available at: <https://author.pure3d.eu/>

4. **Create and name the dataset:** a new Dataset in a DANS Data Station of your choice (section 3.1.4) should be created, and given the title of the 3DSE edition (here: "3D scholarly edition for the "Diaconie Weeshuis", Amsterdam (1656-1888)." In the DANS Data Station Archaeology).
5. The **"project.yaml"** file should be opened on the local hard drive in a text editor, and then the metadata should be copied to the appropriate metadata fields in the data station. For example, the "abstract" information in the .yaml file is copied into the "description field" of the data station.
6. **Save** the information to the Data Station and check the result. Information in the data station can be updated and adjusted at any time.

Figure 4.3 below illustrates the result of steps 1-6. The project now has a persistent identifier (DOI), and a citation record is available. The example also shows the access licence that is connected to the project. If applicable, the licence can be adjusted.

DANS Data Station Archaeology

DANS Data Station Archaeology >

3D scholarly edition for the "Diaconie Weeshuis", Amsterdam (1656-1888).

Version 1.0

T. Lanjouw, 2025, "3D scholarly edition for the "Diaconie Weeshuis", Amsterdam (1656-1888).", <https://doi.org/10.17026/AR/Z2FNTQ>, DANS Data Station Archaeology, V1

Cite Dataset ▾ Learn about [Data Citation Standards](#).

Access Dataset ▾

Contact Owner Share

Dataset Metrics ⓘ

41 Downloads ⓘ

Description ⓘ This dataset belongs to a "3D scholarly edition" about the "Diaconie weeshuis", a historic building in Amsterdam. In the latter half of the 17th century, the Diaconie Weeshuis, an Amsterdam orphanage managed by a protestant church, proudly overlooked the Amstel river. It was located on former 'Vlooienburg', an island constructed in the Amstel river for urban expansion around 1600. The orphanage was constructed in 1656, after the plague epidemic of 1654-55 which had turned many children to orphanhood. It was sited on a previously unbuilt quay area on the edge of Vlooienburg. To make space for this large building, a new strip of land had to be reclaimed from the Amstel river. This building stood here for 230 years before it got replaced by a new orphanage building in Neogothic style in 1888. Neither of the two buildings have survived, and especially for the older building there are only few remaining visual sources. This 3D reconstruction for the first time synthesises these sources into a model of this lost piece of architecture of Amsterdam.

Subject ⓘ Arts and Humanities

Keyword ⓘ 3D model, Amsterdam, Vlooienburg, historical architecture reconstruction, Diaconie Weeshuis

License/Data Use Agreement CC-BY-4.0

Files Metadata **Terms** Versions

Figure 4.3: Main/landing page of a 3DSE dataset in Data Station

The main screen does not show all metadata fields. The tab "Metadata" at the bottom of the screen provides access to the complete metadata record of the 3DSE. The complete metadata record (based on the "project.yaml" file) is provided in the figure below (Figure 4.4a & 4.4b). Each section can be expanded or closed to get access to their metadata fields.

Citation Metadata	
Persistent Identifier	doi:10.17026/AR/Z2FNTQ
Publication Date	2025-05-20
Title	3D scholarly edition for the "Diaconie Weeshuis", Amsterdam (1656-1888).
Subtitle	The 3D reconstruction of one of Amsterdam's disappeared buildings.
Alternative URL	https://editions.pure3d.eu/project/7/edition/1/index.html
Author	T. Lanjouw (UvA) - ORCID: 0000-0003-3602-4453
Point of Contact	Use email button above to contact. Lanjouw, Tijm (UvA)
Description	This dataset belongs to a "3D scholarly edition" about the "Diaconie weeshuis", a historic building in Amsterdam. In the latter half of the 17th century, the Diaconie Weeshuis, an Amsterdam orphanage managed by a protestant church, proudly overlooked the Amstel river. It was located on former 'Vlooienburg', an island constructed in the Amstel river for urban expansion around 1600. The orphanage was constructed in 1656, after the plague epidemic of 1654-55 which had turned many children to orphanhood. It was sited on a previously unbuilt quay area on the edge of Vlooienburg. To make space for this large building, a new strip of land had to be reclaimed from the Amstel river. This building stood here for 230 years before it got replaced by a new orphanage building in Neogothic style in 1888. Neither of the two buildings have survived, and especially for the older building there are only few remaining visual sources. This 3D reconstruction for the first time synthesises these sources into a model of this lost piece of architecture of Amsterdam.
Subject	Arts and Humanities
Keyword	3D model Amsterdam Vlooienburg historical architecture reconstruction Diaconie Weeshuis
Language	English
Producer	
Production Date	2020
Production Location	Amsterdam
Contributor	Editor: Mikko Kriek
Funding Information	NWO: 360-60-130 PDI-SSH
Distributor	
Distribution Date	2025-04-04
Depositor	Lanjouw, Tijm
Deposit Date	2025-04-04
Time Period	Start Date: 1660; End Date: 1888
Date of Collection	Start Date: 2020; End Date: 2020 Start Date: 2024; End Date: 2025
Data Type	computer graphic reconstruction; written narrative
Series	PURE3D: This edition was created for the PURE3D project as part of a suite of pilot projects that helped to develop the PURE3D infrastructure. The models were made in 2019 and 2020 by the 4D Research Lab of the University of Amsterdam for the Diaspora and Identity project, funded by the NWO. They were originally used for a touchscreen VR application that was on display in the Jewish Museum, Amsterdam, for the duration of the exhibit "Waterlooplein, the buurt binnenstebuiten". Some of the models have since been reused or served as test cases in various academic projects, including Pure3D, 5D culture, and Amsterdam Time Machine.
Software	Blender, Version: 3.6 Smithsonian Voyager, Version: 0.46.1
Data Source	https://editions.pure3d.eu/project/7/edition/1/index.html

Figure 4.4a: 3DSE Metadata in Data Station

Rights Metadata ^	
Rights Holder ?	4D Research Lab
Personal Data In Dataset? ?	No
Language Of Metadata ?	English

Relation Metadata ^	
Audience ?	History; Archaeology; History of arts and architecture

Archaeology-Specific Metadata ^	
Keyword Getty AAT ?	virtual models

Temporal and Spatial Coverage ^	
Temporal Coverage ?	1660-1888
Spatial Point ?	4.899272054292055 52.367771487937226 Longitude/latitude (degrees)
Spatial Coverage ?	Netherlands
Spatial Coverage (Free Text) ?	Amsterdam; Vlooienburg; Zwanenburgerstraat

Figure 4.4b: 3DSE Metadata in Data Station (continued)

4.4.4. Submitting data files

Now that a metadata record of the 3DSE edition has been created in the DANS Data Station, the following steps illustrate how to submit the data files of the edition(s) to the data station (as well as any additional files), as described in step 3.

7. **Import** all folders and files into the data station, by selecting the top folder. The data station will automatically import all files and keep the files in the correct folder. The data station will recognize duplicate files and will ask the depositor whether to keep all of them or skip the duplicate during the download process. The Data Station will provide a list of all files in a table. The example in the figure below (Figure 4.5) shows that the Diaconie Weeshuis edition consists of 38 files. The data station provides online viewers for common file formats, such as digital images and multimedia files. A viewer for 3D models is not available yet. In the current example, all data related to the edition itself (except the edition.yaml file) were added in a subfolder called "data". The main folder included the edition and project .yaml files, as well as a readme file, and a screencast demonstrating the 3DSE (including the rendered 3D model and articles) as presented through Smithsonian Voyager. See Figure 4.6 for details.

Diaconie Weeshuis

Files Metadata Terms Versions

Change View Table Tree

Search this dataset...

Filter by File Type: All Access: All Sort

1 to 10 of 38 Files Download

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Files Per Page 10

Figure 4.5: Table View

- Activating the **“Tree” view** will show the files per Edition based on the name of the folder provided in step 2 (and 3, in case additional files are submitted). Opening the edition folder will show the 3D model(s) and additional files (in the Articles subfolder) See the figure below (Figure 4.6)

Figure 4.6: Tree View

- The last step of the deposit process concerns the **access management** of the individual files. By default, all files get an open access licence. If any data is copyright protected, or contains personal data, the file access rights should be adjusted. In Figure 4.7 from a mock dataset (the Diaconie Weeshuis dataset does not contain restricted files), the image file “032-5355.jpg” has been put under restricted access. A user can use the “Request Access” button to contact the depositor about this.

Figure 4.7: Managing Restricted Access to individual files

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